

LEARNERS' ATTITUDES TOWARD READING AND THEIR LEVEL OF COMPREHENSION

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 22

Issue 10

Pages: 1248-1259

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2135

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13208129

Manuscript Accepted: 07-09-2024

Learners' Attitudes toward Reading and their Level of Comprehension

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to know the nature of reading attitudes and the reading comprehension level of key stage 2 learners in a total of 135 of Tagpaco and Sinalac Elementary Schools. The reading comprehension questionnaire was adapted from Philippine Informal Reading (Phil-IRI)2018 stories on reading comprehension. The descriptive–correlational design with a modified adopted questionnaire as the main data gathering instrument. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Pearson's product-moment correlation tool in the context of the theories of Skinner's, schema, operant conditioning, attitudes, and the reasoned action model theory. This implies that most respondents believe that reading is important and can contribute to personal and professional growth. However, there is still a need for improvement, as some learners do not prioritize reading or hold negative attitudes toward it. Encouraging more positive attitudes towards reading could have significant advantages in terms of academic achievement and personal development, such as improved reading skills, increased vocabulary, and better critical thinking abilities. The results of this study revealed that promoting positive attitudes toward reading among key stage 2 learners should consider gender differences and be targeted toward specific grade levels, even though factors such as age and parental education may not have a significant impact on attitudes toward reading.

Keywords: *attitudes, level of reading comprehension, key stage 2 learners, reading*

Introduction

Learners who develop a positive attitude towards reading are more likely to enjoy what they read, become good readers, understand what they read better, and have higher academic achievement. Reading proficiency gained in primary school has a favorable or bad impact on a learner's subsequent learning.

The motivation behind one's aim to attain or complete anything can be attributed to attitude. The ability of students to complete a task is significantly influenced by their mood, whether positive or negative. To learn more about how learners, learn and how to best support them, an exploratory study has been conducted on this and other attitudinal dimensions like motivation. Around the world, various factors relating to reading comprehension and attitudes have been studied. This includes but is not limited to, Patterson's (2017) research on the impact and connection between the reading habits of parents and the reading habits of their children.

The act of recognizing, understanding, and comprehending written or printed content is known as reading (Ahmad and Yamat, 2021). According to Sonia and Fisher (2016) that students must understand the text to attain the goal of reading, in which the information is general or specific from the text. Acquiring valuable learning in life is known as comprehension. Students will be more effective in implementing and developing what they have learned and comprehended as a result of the understanding process.

As a result, this study investigates how students' attitudes about reading and their degree of reading comprehension relate to one another. This study intends to shed light on how learners approach reading and how this affects their overall understanding and learning results by a thorough review of several elements, including learner attitudes, reading tactics, and reading preferences. This important topic, give instructors useful knowledge on how to support students more effectively in increasing their attitudes about reading and comprehension levels.

Therefore, the state "shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education to all levels and shall take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all," according to Article XIV, Section 1 of the Constitution. Since basic education is the cornerstone of students' education, it follows that all educational institutions should strive to provide high-quality instruction.

Moreover, the Constitution's Article XIV Section 3 requires that "all educational institutions, shall, among other things, encourage critical and creative thinking." The basic topics, including English, Math, Science, Filipino, and Araling Panlipunan, are tested of the students. The way the questions are written is intended to gauge students' capacity for critical thought.

Additionally, Every Child a Reader Program (ECARP) in DepEd Order no. is a national program that addresses the thrust of DepED to make every Filipino child a reader at his/her own level. It is designed to equip elementary pupils with strategic reading and writing skills to make them independent young readers and writers. It also provides a year-long training for teachers to make them multi-literate and independent problem solvers. It offers schools and other settings a range of evidence-based interventions for children struggling to read and write in primary schools. The Specialist Teaching of Reading service was formerly known as 'Every Child a Reader' (ECaR). Narrowing the attainment gap for disadvantaged children across the school.

Thus, learning to read is about listening and understanding as well as working out what is printed on the page. Through hearing stories, children are exposed to a wide range of words. This helps them build their own vocabulary and improve their understanding when they

listen, which is vital as they start to read. ECARP is implemented through the following components: Reading Recovery (RR), Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI), and Philippine Word Lists in English (PWLE). Reading Recovery (RR) is an early literacy intervention designed to reduce reading and writing difficulties in schools.

Hence, the Department of Education (DepEd), formulated an assessment tool called Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) that aimed to be used as a classroom-based assessment tool to measure and describe learners' reading performance. Information gathered from the assessment can help classroom teachers design and provide appropriate reading instruction for their learners. In DepEd Order no. 14 s. 2018, provides the guidelines for the administration of the revised Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI). The PHIL-IRI tool was administered within the first or second month of the school year. Each instrument is composed of a 20-item comprehension test based on a set of leveled passages for each grade level covering Grades 3 to 6 in Filipino and Grades 4 to 6 in English.

The performance of Tagpaco and Sinalac Elementary Schools in the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) for the academic year 2022-2023 in pre-test showed that 134 learners population from grades 4-6, 76% of learners from Grades 4 to 6 fall under the frustration level in our pre-test administration. Since reading involves all subjects. Learners need to read the question in order to answer the question. Fundamentally, in order to improve Phil-IRI, a learner's reading comprehension needs to be assessed. But also strategically assess what affects their comprehension and if leisure reading truly affects their comprehension based on research. Thus this research is formulated.

Research Questions

This study determined the level of reading comprehension of intermediate Learners of Tagpaco and Sinalac Elementary School, SY 2022-2023. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following problems:

1. What are the learners' attitudes toward reading?
2. What is the learners' level of reading comprehension?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the learners' attitudes toward reading and their level of reading comprehension?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and their attitudes toward reading?
5. What action plan can be designed based on the findings of this study?

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive–correlational design was used for this study. This study is descriptive because it describes the learners' attitudes toward reading and their comprehension level. Moreover, this study is correlational because it deals with the significant relationship between the learners' attitudes toward reading and their comprehension level. Descriptive research is summarized using descriptive statistics. Correlational research designs measure two or more relevant variables and assess a relationship between or among them.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were the grade 4-6 learners of Tagpaco and Sinalac Elementary Schools who were officially enrolled in the school year 2022-2023. Learners' profile data presents the demographic profile of the 135 respondents in the study. The respondents were composed of 67 (49.6%) male and 68 (50.4%) female key stage 2 learners. In terms of grade level, 35 (25.9%) were in Grade 4, 45 (33.3%) were in Grade 5, and 55 (40.7%) were in Grade 6. Regarding age, 51 (37.8%) were 10 years old, 41 (30.4%) were 11 years old, and 22 (16.3%) were 12 years old. Only 5 respondents (3.7%) were 13 years old or above. There is one section in each level. These grade levels were considered because of their distinct characteristics as learners.

The sampling used in this study were the cluster sampling, it is when a researcher chooses specific people for a method of sampling where the population is divided into clusters or groups, and a random sample of clusters were selected for inclusion in the study. Tagpaco and Sinalac Elementary Schools can be considered as clusters or groups, and have chosen to sample all learners from each selected school. Stratified sampling, on the other hand, is a sampling method where the population is divided into subgroups or strata, and a random sample is taken from each stratum. The strata were the different grade levels (grade 4, 5, and 6), and were chosen to include learners from each grade level in the study.

Hence, the sampling method can be described as cluster sampling because all learners from each school were selected, and stratified sampling because the learners from each grade level were included. This method can help ensure that the sample is representative of the population and can improve the precision of the estimates. It is believed that there can be a wider range of struggles that a learner may encounter during fourth grade to 12th grade. However, fourth-grade pupils were found to have intellectual curiosity, although they are less imaginative than third-graders. Generally, based on the stages of reading by Jeanne Chall (1983), as cited by Mirasol (2020) Grades 4–6, readers on these levels tend to read to absorb new concepts and knowledge, to feel the experiences, and to adapt new attitudes, generally from a single viewpoint. These characteristics are highly important for educators to consider in the day-to-day lesson to be able to provide rich learning opportunities for them.

Table 1. Respondents of the Study

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Population</i>	
	Male	Female
Grade 4(Section)		
Friendly	14	13
Diligent	12	17
Grade 5(Section)		
Adorable	13	10
Loyal	12	10
Grade 6(Section)		
Hospitable	8	5
Love	8	13
Total	67	68
Grand Total	135	

Instruments

In this study, the questionnaire on attitudes toward reading which Tunnell, et al (1988) developed was adapted with modifications. It was composed of 20 questions and the items were translated into Visayan dialect. The reading comprehension questionnaire adapted Philippine Informal Reading (Phil-IRI) stories on reading comprehension. Three parts compromised the research instrument: part 1 on respondents’ demographic profile, part 2 on attitudes toward reading, and part 3 on reading comprehension. A statistical analysis of reliability and validity on the attitudes toward reading was conducted using Cronbach’s Alpha based on the data generated from 30 respondent’s questionnaire. The attitudes towards reading part were tested for reliability, the results which are as follows: The pilot data revealed that the study variables have Cronbach’s alpha of 0.689 which is described as acceptable. Based on the findings, the instrument has at least acceptable internal consistency. This result indicated that the instrument is reliable and is recommended for final survey dissemination.

Table 2. Reliability Statistics Result

<i>Study Variables</i>	<i>Cronbach’s Alpha</i>	<i>Description</i>
Attitude towards Reading	.689	Acceptable

Procedure

When the questionnaires were finally approved, validated, passed the reliability test and ready for distribution, the next step was to determine the date as to when and where questionnaires would be distributed. A letter of request was prepared, checked and noted by the dean and the adviser, addressed to the district supervisor and school in-charge of Tagpaco and Sinalac Elementary Schools for approval of the administration of the survey and questionnaire. The data was tabulated, analyzed and interpreted.

The researcher asked the help of the class advisers to orient the learners in their classrooms regarding the mechanics on how to answer the survey, reading comprehension questionnaire and to administer the distribution of it. The respondents were made to understand the importance of the study through their teacher advisers, even as their honest answers were sought regarding vital information on their perspectives/perceptions and assessments as specified in the letter of request. Prior to the filling up of the questionnaire, the prior informed consent of the respondents was secured using the SPC informed consent form for research. Immediately after the respondents have answered and returned the questionnaires to their advisers, these were collected by the class advisers. The researcher himself retrieved the questionnaires from the adviser, then she personally acknowledged the teacher and learners for their active participation and contribution to the study with a certificate of appreciation.

Table 3. Scoring Guidelines

A. For Reading Comprehension

<i>Score</i>	<i>Overall Score</i>	<i>Description</i>
5	21-25	Excellent
4	16-20	Very Good
3	11-15	Good
2	6-10	Fair
1	0-5	Poor

B. For Attitude Towards Reading

<i>Score</i>	<i>Interval</i>	<i>Description</i>
5	4.50- 5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.50- 4.49	Agree
3	2.50 - 3.49	Undecided
2	1.50 - 2.49	Disagree
1	1.00 - 1.49	Strongly Disagree

Data Analysis

Problems 1, 2, and 3, sought to find the learner's attitudes toward reading and the level of reading comprehension of the respondents in the study, they used frequency count, percentage mean, and standard deviation.

Problems 4 and 5 used multiple regression analysis with dummy variables, to test differences in the level of reading comprehension when grouped according to demographic and attitudes toward reading. For Problem 6 Pearson R was used to measure the relationship between the attitude towards reading and the level of reading comprehension at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results and discussions of the data gathered in the study. These results are presented in tabular form for convenient analyses and interpretation to give clear discussions of the answers to the problem of this study based on the statement of the problems focusing the learners' demographic profile, in terms of sex, parent's monthly income, father's highest educational attainment, mother's highest educational attainment, and family income.

Problem 1: What are the learners' attitudes toward reading?

Table 4. Attitudes Toward Reading Among Key stage 2 Learners

Indicators	Mean \pm SD	Description
1. Reading is an important part of my life.	4.60 \pm .67	Strongly Agree
2. I read often in my spare time.	3.80 \pm 1.21	Agree
3. I believe that better jobs are available to those with good reading skills.	4.41 \pm .92	Agree
4. I would rather read a book than watch TV.	4.17 \pm .98	Agree
5. I like to buy books and have a place to keep them at home.	3.78 \pm 1.15	Agree
6. When I find the kind of books I like, reading can be enjoyable.	4.43 \pm .96	Agree
7. I like to share a good book with a friend.	4.26 \pm .94	Agree
8. I usually check out a book when I go to the library.	4.06 \pm .99	Agree
9. Reading books is a waste of time.	2.19 \pm 1.61	Disagree
10. I would like to belong to a book club.	3.99 \pm 1.29	Agree
11. Reading makes me feel good.	4.35 \pm 1.18	Agree
12. I seldom read except when I have to.	3.02 \pm 1.41	Undecided
13. Reading is an enjoyable way to learn.	4.54 \pm .94	Strongly Agree
14. I like to read before I go to bed.	4.12 \pm 1.12	Agree
15. I often look for extra books or articles to read about something which interests me.	4.13 \pm 1.00	Agree
16. I like to look through the books at the library.	4.21 \pm .97	Agree
17. Reading is boring.	2.40 \pm 1.54	Disagree
18. I usually read books during vacation times.	3.86 \pm 1.06	Agree
19. I would like to someday write a book.	3.53 \pm 1.44	Agree
20. I am not scared to read literature with many words that I do not know.	3.90 \pm 1.29	Agree
Total Measure	3.89 \pm .46	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49, Strongly Disagree; 1.50-2.49, Disagree; 2.50-3.49, Undecided; 3.50-4.49, Agree; 4.50-5.00, Strongly Agree

Attitudes toward reading among key stage 2 learners are an important topic of study as they can provide insights into how individuals perceive and engage with reading. This information can be useful for educators and policymakers in designing effective reading programs and interventions to promote literacy skills. Understanding the attitudes towards reading can also help identify potential barriers or challenges that individuals may face in developing and maintaining reading habits. In this context, the present study aimed to examine the attitudes towards reading among key stage 2 learners using a set of indicators that cover various aspects of reading behavior and perception.

The five indicators with the highest mean scores in the attitudes towards reading among key stage 2 learners survey were "Reading is an important part of my life," "I believe that better jobs are available to those with good reading skills," "When I find the kind of books I like, reading can be enjoyable," "Reading makes me feel good," and "Reading is an enjoyable way to learn." The results indicate that the surveyed key stage 2 learners have a positive attitude towards reading, and consider it an essential part of their lives. They recognize the potential benefits of reading, including personal growth, career opportunities, and intellectual stimulation.

The finding that "Reading is an important part of my life" had the highest mean score suggests that the surveyed key stage 2 learners consider reading to be a significant aspect of their identity and daily routine. This positive attitude towards reading may stem from their belief that it can lead to better job opportunities, which was the second-highest rated indicator. The respondents recognize that reading can enhance their skills and knowledge, and potentially increase their chances of success in their future careers.

The indicators "When I find the kind of books I like, reading can be enjoyable," "Reading makes me feel good," and "Reading is an enjoyable way to learn" all had high mean scores, indicating that the key stage 2 learners surveyed find pleasure and satisfaction in reading. These positive feelings may motivate them to continue reading and pursue it as a hobby or a means of personal development.

In conclusion, the high mean scores of the top five indicators suggest that the key stage 2 learners surveyed have a positive attitude

towards reading, recognize its potential benefits, and find enjoyment in it. These findings highlight the importance of promoting a reading culture among learners and encouraging them to view reading as a valuable and fulfilling activity.

In contrast to the top 5 indicators, the bottom 5 indicators reflect less enthusiastic attitudes toward reading among the surveyed key stage 2 learners. It is apparent that a small proportion of the learners surveyed may view reading as a waste of time or find it boring. These results suggest that some learners may not find reading as engaging or as enjoyable as others, which could potentially impact their reading habits and skills.

However, it is important to note that even the lowest-scoring indicators received mean scores that reflect agreement or neutrality towards the statements rather than outright disagreement. This indicates that despite some negative attitudes towards reading, most key stage 2 learners still recognize its value and may be open to further encouragement to develop positive attitudes towards reading.

In general, key stage 2 learners have a favorable attitude towards reading, as shown by a total mean score of 3.89, which is categorized as "Agree." This implies that most respondents believe that reading is important and can contribute to personal and professional growth. However, there is still a need for improvement, as some learners do not prioritize reading or hold negative attitudes toward it. Encouraging more positive attitudes towards reading could have significant advantages in terms of academic achievement and personal development, such as improved reading skills, increased vocabulary, and better critical thinking abilities. Therefore, it is important to continue to promote and support reading among key stage 2 learners.

Hence, Avallone (2005) as cited by Mirasol (2020), assessed the academic reading attitude of fourth-graders, and the results revealed that the attitude toward reading has a significant role in reading progression. The result seems to challenge the necessary intervention from the teacher to help the learners establish greater positivity of attitudes toward academic reading since all activities in school entail the act of reading.

Problem 2: What is the learners' level of reading comprehension?

Table 5. *Reading Comprehension among the Key stage 2 Learners*

Grade 6 (n=55)					
Score	Reading Comprehension Level	F	%	Mean ± SD	
21-25	Excellent	1	1.8		
16-20	Very Good	3	5.5	10.22±3.73	
11-15	Good	21	38.2	(Fair)	
6-10	Fair	24	43.6		
0-5	Poor	6	10.9		
Grade 5 (n=45)					
Score	Reading Comprehension Level	F	%	Mean ± SD	
16-20	Excellent	1	2.2		
12-15	Very Good	10	22.2	8.89±3.34	
8-11	Good	18	40.0	(Good)	
4-7	Fair	14	31.1		
0-3	Poor	2	4.4		
Grade 4 (n=35)					
Score	Reading Comprehension Level	F	%	Mean ± SD	
16-20	Excellent	2	5.7		
12-15	Very Good	6	17.1	8.51±3.88	
8-11	Good	11	31.4	(Good)	
4-7	Fair	15	42.9		
0-3	Poor	1	2.9		

Table 5 presents the reading comprehension levels and corresponding mean scores among the key stage 2 learners grouped by grade level. The results show that the majority of the learners in all grades fall under the "Fair" category, with only a few reaching the "Excellent" and "Very Good" categories.

In Grade 6, 1 student achieved an "Excellent" score of 21-25, while 3 learners scored in the "Very Good" range of 16-20. Nearly 38% scored in the "Good" range of 11-15. Meanwhile, 24 learners, or 43.6% scored in the "Fair" range of 6-10, and 6 learners, or 10.9% scored in the "Poor" range of 0-5.

For Grade 5, only 1 student scored in the "Excellent" range of 16-20, while 10 learners, or 22.2% scored in the "Very Good" range of 12-15. The majority of the learners, 18 or 40%, scored in the "Good" range of 8-11, while 14 learners or 31.1% scored in the "Fair" range of 4-7, and only 2 learners or 4.4% scored in the "Poor" range of 0-3.

In Grade 4, 2 learners achieved an "Excellent" score of 16-20, while 6 learners or 17.1% scored in the "Very Good" range of 12-15. The majority of the learners, 11 or 31.4%, scored in the "Good" range of 8-11, while 15 learners, or 42.9% scored in the "Fair" range of 4-7, and only 1 student or 2.9% scored in the "Poor" range of 0-3.

The results indicate that the majority of key stage 2 learners have only "Fair" reading comprehension levels, with only a few reaching the higher levels of "Very Good" and "Excellent". This highlights the need for interventions and strategies

that can improve the reading comprehension skills of key stage 2 learners to help them achieve academic success and lifelong learning.

Looking at the mean scores for each grade level, the key stage 2 learners in Grade 6 had the highest mean score of 10.22 (SD= 3.73), which falls under the "Fair" category. Grade 5 had a mean score of 8.89 (SD=3.34), also falling under the "Good" category. Lastly, Grade 4 had a mean score of 8.51 (SD=3.88), which is close to the lower end of the "Good" category. Overall, these mean scores suggest that key stage 2 learners have a good level of reading comprehension, but there is still room for improvement in all grade levels. It is important to note that the standard deviations for each grade level are relatively high, indicating a wide range of scores and potential variability in reading comprehension ability among key stage 2 learners.

Mirasol (2020) evaluated that the attitudes in reading recreationally decline as pupil's progress from Grade 4 to Grade 6. On the other hand, results revealed that there is no significant difference in the academic reading attitude according to grade level. This implies that the kind of reading demands in school helps the learners engage in academic reading consistently. It could be said that for one to write one has to read. Along this line, Memiş and Kandemir (2019) noted that reading comprehension as an ability is the single most important means of obtaining information. Additionally, Habibian et al. (2015) maintained that for students to perform well, they must attain a certain level of mastery in reading so that they would be able to understand the curriculum adequately to their advantage. Beyond doubt, reading comprehension is one of the most investigated constructs. It has been investigated in multiple contextualization's alongside different variables.

Problem 3: Is there a significant relationship between the learners' attitudes toward reading and their level of reading comprehension?

Table 6. *Relationship between the learners' attitudes toward reading and their level of reading comprehension*

Variable	Reading Comprehension		Remark
	r-value	p-value	
Attitude toward Reading	-.083 ^{ns}	.339	Not significant

Note: Analysis is based on Pearson Correlation; ns-not significant (p>.05)

Table 6 presents the relationship between the respondents' level of reading comprehension and their attitudes toward reading. The results indicate that there is no significant correlation between the two variables, as evidenced by the non-significant r-value of -.083 and p-value of .339. This implies that key stage 2 learners' attitudes toward reading do not necessarily reflect their level of reading comprehension.

This finding is consistent with some previous studies that have shown a weak or non-existent relationship between attitudes toward reading and reading comprehension, Guthrie, Wigfield, & VonSecker (2000). However, other studies have found a positive correlation between attitudes toward reading and reading comprehension Guthrie, Schafer, & Huang, (2001; Tse, (2001) as cited by Wigfield et al. (2016).

It is important to note that while attitudes towards reading may not directly affect reading comprehension, they can indirectly impact academic performance. Learners who have positive attitudes towards reading are more likely to engage in reading activities, which in turn can improve their reading skills and academic achievement McKenna, Kear, and Ellsworth (1995). Therefore, it is still crucial to promote positive attitudes towards reading among key stage 2 learners, even if it may not have a direct effect on their reading comprehension.

Thus, this result suggests that there is no significant relationship between the respondents' level of reading comprehension and their attitudes toward reading. However, promoting positive attitudes towards reading can still have numerous benefits in terms of academic achievement and personal growth.

The implication of this result is that while there may not be a direct link between attitudes toward reading and reading comprehension, it is still important to encourage positive attitudes toward reading among key stage 2 learners. This is because having a positive attitude towards reading can lead to increased engagement in reading activities, which in turn can improve reading skills and academic achievement. Additionally, promoting positive attitudes towards reading can have personal growth benefits, such as increased empathy, better communication skills, and improved critical thinking abilities. Therefore, educators and parents should continue to promote a love of reading among key stage 2 learners, even if there may not be a direct relationship between attitudes toward reading and reading comprehension.

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and their attitudes toward reading?

Table 7 shows the results of a multiple regression analysis conducted to determine the relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and their attitudes toward reading. The results indicate that only sex and grade level have a significant relationship with attitudes towards reading, while age, mother education, and father education do not.

Table 7. Relationship between the Respondents' Demographic Profile and their Attitudes toward Reading

Variables	Estimate	SE	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Sex (Female)	.177	.076	2.326	.022	Significant
Grade Level					
Grade 5	-.023	.118	-.192	.848	Not significant
Grade 6	-.353	.129	-2.744	.007	Significant
Age					
9 years old	.053	.257	.208	.836	Not significant
10 years old	.087	.233	.375	.709	Not significant
11 years old	.101	.225	.452	.652	Not significant
12 years old	.149	.229	.649	.518	Not significant
Mother Education					
Elementary Level	.130	.163	.802	.424	Not significant
Elementary Graduate	.184	.165	1.114	.268	Not significant
High School Level	.163	.166	.981	.328	Not significant
High School Graduate	.068	.172	.396	.693	Not significant
College Level	-.287	.205	-1.401	.164	Not significant
College Graduate	.094	.193	.484	.629	Not significant
Father Education					
Elementary Level	.342	.257	1.333	.185	Not significant
Elementary Graduate	.435	.280	1.553	.123	Not significant
High School Level	.238	.265	.901	.369	Not significant
High School Graduate	.213	.291	.731	.466	Not significant
College Level	.052	.302	.175	.862	Not significant
College Graduate	.342	.342	1.002	.319	Not significant

Note: Analysis is based on Multiple Regression with Dummy Variables; *significant ($p < .05$)

ns-not significant ($p > .05$); Ireference category: male for sex, Grade 4 for grade level, 13+ years old for age, no education for mother and father education

Specifically, being female has a significant positive relationship with attitudes towards reading ($p < .05$), with female respondents having a mean attitude score of .177 higher than male respondents. Meanwhile, grade level also has a significant relationship with attitudes toward reading, with grade 6 respondents having a mean attitude score of .353 lower than grade 4 respondents ($p < .05$). The lack of significant relationships between attitudes towards reading and other demographic variables suggests that factors such as age and parental education level may not have a significant impact on attitudes towards reading among key stage 2 learners. This suggests that these factors may not be significant predictors of attitudes toward reading in this particular context. While previous studies by Eijansantos et al. (2020) have shown that gender is found to have an influence on attitude toward print reading with females manifesting better attitudes.

According to Osabinyi (2023), he concluded that family structure can have some impact on parental involvement in early reading literacy skills achievements for lower primary school children. The study recommended that parents and teachers must be aware of the significant contribution they can make to their children's learning by providing a stimulating environment around language, reading, and writing, as well as supporting the school's literacy agenda at home, both during the early years of schooling and later years. It can be concluded that parents are willing to engage when they believe the schools are open and eager to facilitate their engagement.

In summary, the results of this study suggest that promoting positive attitudes toward reading among key stage 2 learners should consider gender differences and be targeted toward specific grade levels, even though factors such as age and parental education may not have a significant impact on attitudes toward reading.

Conclusions

Based on the findings and analysis of the study, certain conclusions may be stated.

As postulated under the attitudes theory, it was discussed that attitudes toward reading may vary through gender, text type, and genre. The study found that female readers have a more positive attitude toward academic texts while male readers have a more positive attitude toward recreational texts. It can be noted that the results of multiple regression analysis were conducted to determine the relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and their attitudes toward reading. The results indicate that only sex and grade level have a significant relationship with attitudes towards reading, while age, mother education, and father education do not.

The lack of significant relationships between attitudes towards reading and other demographic variables suggests that factors such as age and parental education level may not have a significant impact on attitudes towards reading among key stage 2 learners. This suggests that these factors may not be significant predictors of attitudes toward reading in this particular context.

Similarly, the findings of this study provided some evidence of postulating that this considers the following theoretical expressions that are related to reading: (a) people with more positive intentions are more likely to perform better than those who have less positive intentions, and (b) people who experience more social density are more likely to perform than those who have less. The effect presents

the relationship between the respondents' level of reading comprehension and their attitudes toward reading. Thus, the result suggests that there is no significant relationship between the respondents' level of reading comprehension and their attitudes toward reading. However, promoting positive attitudes towards reading can still have numerous benefits in terms of academic achievement and personal growth.

The implication of this result is that while there may not be a direct link between attitudes toward reading and reading comprehension, it is still important to encourage positive attitudes toward reading among key stage 2 learners. This is because having a positive attitude towards reading can lead to increased engagement in reading activities, which in turn can improve reading skills and academic achievement.

Moreover, viewing the findings, this is likely to happen when teachers and some parents tend to give reinforcement in every step of the process of reading (Law of Shaping) to the students to ensure the reading and understanding of what they read, thus, it helps the students come up with their own opinion about reading and most importantly develop their attitudes towards reading. The results indicate among key stage 2 learners have a favorable attitude towards reading, as shown by a total mean score of 3.89, which is categorized as "Agree." This implies that most respondents believe that reading is important and can contribute to personal and professional growth. However, there is still a need for improvement, as some learners do not prioritize reading or hold negative attitudes toward it. Encouraging more positive attitudes towards reading could have significant advantages in terms of academic achievement and personal development, such as improved reading skills, increased vocabulary, and better critical thinking abilities. Therefore, it is important to continue to promote and support reading among key stage 2 learners.

Thus, this study concludes based on the assumption that the readers' prior knowledge directly impacts new learning situations. Reading theorists view schema theory as a "framework" that organizes knowledge in memory but puts information into the correct "slots," each of which contains related parts. The mean scores suggest that key stage 2 learners have a good level of reading comprehension, but there is still room for improvement in all grade levels. It is important to note that the standard deviations for each grade level are relatively high, indicating a wide range of scores and potential variability in reading comprehension ability among key stage 2 learners. This highlights the need for interventions and strategies that can improve the reading comprehension skills of key stage 2 learners to help them achieve academic success and lifelong learning.

The following recommendations are offered to enhance good attitudes about reading among key stage 2 learners. These recommendations are based on the results and discussions that were presented above.

Reading teachers may develop gender-specific reading interventions that are devised to suit the requirements of male learners and to encourage a more favorable attitude toward reading among male learners. For instance, schools can create reading programs that are geared toward guys by including reading materials that feature sports-related literature, graphic novels, and action or adventure stories. Other options include graphic novels.

School administrators may develop and encourage reading at a young age since it helps children grow up to have a more favorable perspective on the activity of reading. These programs can include the establishment of reading nooks, the provision of access to a wide range of reading materials, and the performance of storytelling sessions for younger learners.

School administrators may create a school-wide reading challenge, to foster reading and learning. It is significant so that participation in reading and positive attitudes toward reading may develop.

School administrators may conduct teacher training on promoting positive attitudes toward reading. It is important to provide training and assistance for the parents and caregivers of these learners. Nonetheless, the involvement and support of parents are crucial components in the process of cultivating favorable attitudes about reading.

Schools may conduct surveys to evaluate the effectiveness of interventions, to increase positive attitudes towards reading and reading achievement as evidenced by survey results. This may include encouraging parents to read with their children, giving access to reading resources, and modeling great reading habits.

For future research, studying the influence of parental involvement will be the subject. Although the level of education of the parents was not found to be a significant predictor of reading attitudes in this study, investigating the impact of parental involvement in reading activities at home, such as reading aloud and providing access to reading materials, might provide a better understanding of the role that parents play in shaping reading attitudes.

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<https://www.google.com/search?client=avast3&q=map+of+the+philippines&oq=map+of+the+&aqs=avast.1.69i57j017.3824j0j4&ie=UTF-8#imgrc=nAVJjhvAxX4KNM>
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